

Local Government in Austria

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Structure of Local Government

4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Austria: An Introduction

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Like in many other European countries, the first efforts to merge municipalities in Austria started in the 1960s. While the municipal structures in the western *Länder* of Austria (Vorarlberg, Tirol, Salzburg and Upper-Austria) were already organized in larger units, Lower Austria, Burgenland, Styria and, to some extent Carinthia, were characterized by small-scale municipalities.

Thus, in Lower Austria the number of municipalities decreased from 1,652 municipalities in the year 1965 to 573 municipalities as of now. In Burgenland the amalgamation process started in 1971 by merging the 319 municipalities into 138. Due to later municipal separations, the number of today is 171. With the municipal structural reform in Carinthia in 1973 the number of municipalities was reduced from 242 to 121 municipalities. Again due to some later municipal separations Carinthia today has 132 municipalities. The most recent municipal structural reform in Austria took place from 2010 to 2015 in Styria. The number of municipalities decreased from 542 to 287. This reform also affected the Styrian districts by reducing their number from 17 to 13.

Similar to Switzerland, amalgamations in Austria are driven either by the municipalities themselves (bottom-up) or by the *Länder* (top-down). The process of the most recent structural reform in Styria was driven by the *Land*. Accompanying measures, direct involvement of the affected municipalities through participation and financial incentives were intended to ensure that the amalgamations of municipalities proposed by the *Land* were voluntary. Due to strong resistance of numerous municipalities, the structural reform needed in the end both voluntary and coercive mergers.

However, from the current 2,100 municipalities in Austria only about 70 municipalities have a population of more than 10,000 inhabitants. From the 8.8 million inhabitants in Austria one third of the population lives in the metropolitan area of Vienna.⁷⁴ Hence, Austria has a very fragmented and small-structured municipal landscape.

One reason for the reluctance to territorial reforms in Austria is the clear preference for inter-municipal cooperation. While there is no political program for amalgamations in Austria, the federal government, the *Länder* and the local government associations support the further development of inter-municipal cooperation.

⁷⁴ KDZ, 'Stadtregion Wien' (*stadtregionen.at*, 2019) <<https://www.stadtregionen.at/wien>> accessed 11 November 2019.

Since 2011 the constitutional law to strengthen the powers of municipalities⁷⁵ significantly enlarges the rights of municipalities to establish inter-municipal associations, even across *Länder* borders, primarily to increase service efficiency not only in their own competences, but also in transferred competences. Its implementation was accelerated as a result of the financial crisis and existing budget restrictions aimed to reduce costs by a reorganization of local public services and a new way of managing local and regional authorities' payrolls. Moreover, *Länder* programs to encourage local authorities to modernize their services and to use innovative approaches have been also introduced. Currently all *Länder* provide incentives for inter-municipal cooperation, some of them even tie their transfer payments (in the financial equalization) to municipalities to inter-municipal cooperation. And the present program of the federal government (2020-2024)⁷⁶ promotes to abolish the VAT for inter-municipal cooperation to facilitate co-operations and make them more attractive.

Inter-municipal cooperation in Austria has a long tradition and is based on the principle of voluntariness. Nonetheless, the cooperativeness of municipalities is still rather weak. The often long and resource intensive initiation processes, interest conflicts or only the reluctance to give up own structures for joint projects still hinders inter-municipal cooperation.

In general, all municipal tasks or services in Austria, with the legal competence being anchored in the Federal Constitution, can be carried out inter-municipally. Limitations apply only to the legal form of cooperation: e.g. governing powers cannot be carried out by a private company (municipal housing inspectorate, municipal registry of births, marriages and deaths, municipal taxes etc.).

The main inter-municipal cooperation fields in Austria are:

- supply and disposal (e.g. water and waste);
- regional development and tourism;
- sports and leisure infrastructure (public swimming pools, sport halls, event centers etc.);
- social services (social welfare associations, retirement homes etc.);
- education (kinder garden, elementary and middle schools, residential accommodation for pupils);
- particular governing powers areas (municipal housing inspectorate, municipal registry of births, marriages and deaths etc.);
- internal administrative services like procurement, accounting etc.

⁷⁵ See 60. Bundesverfassungsgesetz: Änderung des Bundes-Verfassungsgesetzes zur Stärkung der Rechte der Gemeinden [Federal Constitutional Law on the Strengthening of the Rights of Municipalities], GP XXIV GABR 1213 AB 1313 S. 112. BR: AB 8526 S. 799.).

⁷⁶ See 'Aus Verantwortung für Österreich. Regierungsprogramm 2020–2024' (Bundeskanzleramt Österreich 2020) 11.

In the past decade, inter-municipal cooperation in location development (business parks, business location etc.) has become more and more important, while fire-services cooperation is still very limited.

Support for inter-municipal cooperation differs from one *Land* to another *Land* in terms of both financial means and non-monetary services. Normally the establishment and management of inter-municipal cooperation are funded by the *Länder*, while cooperation itself or investments are usually not subsidized.

The form of cooperation depends on the tasks and duties. It ranges from informal and non- or little institutionalized cooperation to strong and highly institutionalized cooperation. For certain municipal tasks, the legal form of local authority association (*Gemeindeverbände*) is mandatory.⁷⁷ Scope and tasks are defined by the laws of the Austrian *Länder*.

Figure 7: Forms of Cooperation in Austria.⁷⁸

Inter-municipal cooperation in the framework of an association is possible for a wide range of cooperations, except for governing power services and for profit.

⁷⁷ Cases where cooperation may be imposed by the legislation concern, for example, waste-management associations.

⁷⁸ See Klaus Wirth and Markus Matschek, 'Interkommunale Zusammenarbeit. Möglichkeiten, Grenzen und aktueller Entwicklungsbedarf' (2005) 71 ÖGZ 8.

The administrative association can be seen as the typical model for inter-municipal cooperation, since only municipalities can cooperate in this legal form. Involvement of other legal partners is unlawful. It can be used for either specific services or for all municipal services. The administrative association is neither a public corporation nor a commercial company and therefore not liable for corporation tax unless the association provides private services of general interest, which then will be subject to VAT (value added tax).

The local authority association (*Gemeindeverband*) is a public corporation and is laid down in the Constitution (Article 116(a)).⁷⁹ They are led by elected bodies, in general by the mayor of one member municipality. There is no limitation of the purpose. Since 2011 and as already mentioned before, cross-border municipal cooperation between the Austrian *Länder*, as well as multi-purpose municipal cooperation are possible. Unlike administrative associations, the local authority takes over the services of the member municipalities as a separate body and with its own responsibilities. It is particularly suitable for tasks that require high investments or for politically sensitive areas. Setting up a municipal corporation is no more difficult than setting up a private company.

Involving private partners, the limited liability company (*GesmbH*) is the most common legal form in Austria for inter-municipal cooperation.

Cooperative societies (*Genossenschaften*) have a long tradition in Austria, but only in the field of housing, water supply, and forestry. This legal form has not yet been used for inter-municipal cooperation in Austria.

The federal level in Austria cannot interfere in local government structures since local self-government is safeguarded by the Constitution (Article 116ff). Nevertheless, with the Austrian Conference on Spatial Planning (ÖROK)⁸⁰, founded in 1971 and established by the federal government, the *Länder* and the municipalities spatial development is coordinated at the national level. Thus, the ÖROK plays a crucial role in promoting and developing structural reform approaches.⁸¹ In this context urban regions (*Stadtregionen*) in Austria have gained importance and relevance over the last decade through certain ÖROK initiatives: the current Austrian Spatial Development Concept (ÖREK 2011)⁸² and the partnership 'Cooperation

⁷⁹ The Federal Constitutional Law (Art 116(a)) provides that municipalities may join together – by agreement or by law – to form 'Local Authority Associations' (*Gemeindeverbände*) to deal with common specific matters within their own sphere of competences. The Local Authority Association may be voluntary as well as mandatory. In the first case the approval of the supervisory authority is necessary. This approval must be given under certain conditions specified in the Federal Constitutional Law.

⁸⁰ See Österreichische Raumordnungskonferenz ÖROK, 'Austrian Conference on Spatial Planning. ÖROK' (ÖROK, 2020) <<https://www.oerok.gv.at/english-summary/>> accessed 11 November 2019.

⁸¹ The current ÖROK project 'Fostering Regional Governance' aims at sounding out new approaches for strengthening sustainable integrated development in functional areas.

⁸² See Österreichische Raumordnungskonferenz ÖROK, 'Österreichisches Raumentwicklungskonzept ÖREK 2011' (ÖROK, 2020) <<https://www.oerok.gv.at/?id=224>> accessed 2 August 2019.

Platform Urban Regions'⁸³ with the recommendation 'For an Austrian Policy for Urban Regions'⁸⁴ and the roadmap for implementing the 'Austrian Agenda Urban Regions'⁸⁵ not only successfully established the topic in the public discussion but also gave a boost to the development of urban regions in Austria. A crucial role in promoting urban regions in Austria is played by the Austrian Association of Cities and Towns which not only had the lead of the before mentioned partnership 'Cooperation Platform Urban Regions' but also established the 'Annual Forum of Austrian Urban Regions'⁸⁶ and the platform <www.stadtregionen.at> for active urban regions in Austria in terms of joint planning and implementation. Nevertheless, urban region initiatives often depend on the pioneering spirit and commitment of single stakeholders since they are commonly formalized only by inter-municipal agreements with a low degree of institutionalization.

Finding viable solutions for integrated and sustainable regional development both for urban local governments (ULGs) and rural local governments (RLGs) cooperation without introducing new levels of government has been the objective of the current ÖROK project 'Strengthening regional governance'. The project results (status quo, impulses and perspectives) are summarized in the ÖROK study 'Die regionale Handlungsebene stärken: Status, Impulse & Perspektiven'.⁸⁷

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⁸⁴ See Österreichische Raumordnungskonferenz ÖROK, 'ÖROK-Empfehlung Nr. 55 "Für eine Stadtregionpolitik in Österreich"' (2017) <https://www.oerok.gv.at/fileadmin/Bilder/2.Reiter-Raum_u._Region/5.Empfehlungen/OEROK-Empfehlung_Nr._55_angenommen_HP.pdf> accessed 2 August 2019.

⁸⁵ See Österreichisches Raumentwicklungskonzept ÖREK, 'Roadmap zur Umsetzung der "Agenda Stadtregionen in Österreich"' (ÖREK 2017) <https://www.stadtregionen.at/uploads/files/RoadmapAgendaStadtregionen_FINAL.pdf> accessed 2 August 2019.

⁸⁶ See '6. Österreichischer Stadtregionstag 2018 in Wels' (Österreichischer Städtebund, 10 October 2018) <<https://www.staedtebund.gv.at/services/veranstaltungsergebnisse/veranstaltungsergebnisse-details/artikel/6-oesterreichischer-stadtregionstag-2018-in-wels/>> accessed 2 August 2019.

⁸⁷ Österreichische Raumordnungskonferenz (ÖROK), 'Die regionale Handlungsebene stärken – Status, Impulse und Perspektiven' (paper series no 208, ÖROK 2020) <https://www.oerok.gv.at/fileadmin/user_upload/O__ROK_SR_NR._208__2020__Reg_HE_online-Version.pdf>.

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